

Monitoring growing cracks in aircraft lugs by means of the electro-mechanical impedance method

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Abstract

Lugs are common connecting elements in many fields of engineering, e.g., aircraft and automotive. High stress concentrations at the inner edge of the bolt hole lead to early crack initiation and rapid fatigue crack growth under cyclic loading. However, a complete failure of such components is in most cases not acceptable. This contribution presents a model-based methodology to monitor the crack propagation in aircraft lugs by means of the electro-mechanical impedance method. For this purpose, piezoelectric sensors are permanently attached to the monitored structure. The evaluated structural components are necked, straight and tapered lugs. Crack propagation is analyzed numerically by coupled-field finite element models and experimentally using an impedance analyzer. Simulated and measured frequency spectra of pristine (no crack present) and damaged (a crack of various lengths is present) structures show significant deviations in resonance frequencies which are considered as clear indicators of the present crack. Furthermore, the length of artificially introduced cracks is determined by specific resonance frequency shifts for each lug shape. Crack length estimation based on resonance frequency shifts has already been shown in a recent study for necked double shear lugs, which is now extended for straight and tapered lug shapes. Finally, a discussion on the applicability of the presented crack analysis methodology for structural health monitoring of aircraft lugs under fatigue loading is presented.

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Keywords: EMI method; crack length estimation; SHM; double shear lugs

1. Introduction

Double shear lugs are commonly used connecting elements in many fields of engineering, e.g., automotive and aircraft. In comparison to riveted or adhesively bonded joints, lug connections have the advantage to be easily detachable due to the removable bolt. Furthermore, lug joints act as pivot points, and hence, avoid the introduction of bending moments into the surrounding structure (Schijve and Hoeymakers, 1979). Obviously, lug joints are indispensable for movable connections, e.g., for the mounting and actuation of control surfaces of aircraft. However, lug connections are highly sensitive to fatigue failure due to, e.g., high stress concentrations and fretting corrosion at the lug hole. Even though this disadvantage of lug connections is well known, there have been some incidences in the last decade (Giurgiutiu, 2016; Australian Transport Safety Bureau, 2013). Due to this fact, and to further improve aircraft safety, a reliable method for crack identification would be desirable, including, e.g., crack detection and crack length estimation. In this context the continuous online monitoring of the structure is known by the term structural health monitoring (SHM). Compared to nondestructive testing (NDT), SHM additionally enables the onboard monitoring of mechanical structures during operation. This is possible due to integrated and lightweight sensors mounted directly and permanently on the monitored structure. Any changes in the structure, e.g., by cracks or delaminations, should be identified using a continuous signal processing of sensor readings according to the applied SHM methods (Kralovec and Schagerl, 2020). Examples of state-of-the-art monitoring methods are guided waves (Gschoßmann

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et al., 2016; Humer et al., 2019; Yeasin Bhuiyan et al., 2017), electrical impedance tomography (EIT) by conductive surface layers (Zhao et al., 2019; Wagner et al., 2021, 2023) or direct measurements of the electrical impedance of a structure (Nonn et al., 2018) and the electro-mechanical impedance (EMI) method (Giurgiutiu and Zagrai, 2005; Kralovec and Schagerl, 2017; Antunes et al., 2019). For the present investigations the EMI technique together with piezoelectric wafers to excite and monitor the structural component is used. In the last decades the availability and quality of so-called piezoelectric active wafer sensor (PWAS) improved drastically. These devices are small-size, lightweight and low-cost, and can be used as actor and sensor at the same time, which made them attractive for a wide range of SHM applications, especially for monitoring small structures (Giurgiutiu and Zagrai, 2005).

The present investigation extends the crack identification method for necked double shear lugs already published in Winklberger et al. (2021b,a). In this contribution the presented crack identification method is applied to straight and tapered double shear lugs. Furthermore, the crack length estimation for all lug geometries is improved by a profound peak-tracking algorithm. Additionally, multiple experiments are performed to validate the new crack length estimation procedure.

2. Materials and methods

Fig. 1. Geometry of lug specimens, a) schematic sketch including PWAS position and crack parameters, b) dimensions of straight lug specimen, c) dimensions of tapered lug specimen.

2.1. Lug specimens

All lug specimens are made of aluminum EN-AW 2024 T351 and have geometries based on their lugs in real applications. The lug hole is designed to fit a standard spherical bearing MS14101-07. However, in this study the lug specimens are considered without any bearings and the lug designs are adapted to fit available test rig supports (a clamping possibility is provided for later investigations).

A schematic sketch of investigated lug geometries is depicted in Fig. 1a. The dimensions for the bearing hole $R_i = 11.5085$ mm, the lug outer radius $R_o = 17.5$ mm, the lug thickness $t = 8.71$ mm and the sensor position $x_p = 40$ mm are constant for all geometries. Additionally, each geometry has individual parameters: the necked lug has a transition radius $R_t = 2R_o = 35$ mm and a lug width of $W = 13$ mm, the straight lug has a width of $W = 2R_o = 35$ mm, the tapered lug has a taper angle $\gamma = 45^\circ$. The clamping region of the tapered lug has a thickness of 10 mm. The remaining parameters of the fixing points at the back of each lug geometry are given in Winklberger et al. (2021a), Fig. 1b and Fig. 1c.

In general, fatigue cracks observed in lugs under constant amplitude sinusoidal loading have irregular shapes (Kirkby and Rooke, 1977). Usually, these cracks are idealized by through-cracks, quarter circular and quarter elliptical corner cracks to perform analytical or numerical investigations (Schijve and Hoeymakers, 1979; Boljanović and Maksimović, 2014; Naderi and Iyer, 2015). In the present study through-cracks are investigated as they represent the worst case scenario for cracks in lugs (Schijve and Hoeymakers, 1979). Fig. 1a depicts the crack initiation location β_{in} , which is the angle with respect to the x -axis, and the crack length a_c , which is assumed to be perpendicular to the initiation surface.

2.2. Validated numerical models

The numerical models for the straight and tapered lug are developed based on the validated finite element (FE) model of the necked lug presented in Winklberger et al. (2021a). Due to the strong similarity it is assumed that results generated with newly presented models of straight and tapered lugs also correlate well with measurement data. The numerical investigations are carried out using the software Abaqus CAE. Coupled-field FE models are used to carry out direct-solution steady-state dynamic analysis in order to calculate the steady-state responses for harmonically oscillating loads (Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp., 2019). The simplified lug geometries in numerical simulations

Fig. 2. FE models of a) straight lug, and b) tapered lug.

do not include any chamfers and the M18×1.5 threads (only for necked and straight lug geometry) are modeled as smooth round cylinders with a outer diameter of 18 mm. A linear elastic material model is assumed for all lugs (Young's modulus $E = 73$ GPa, Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.34$, density $\rho = 2.77$ kg/m³, Rayleigh damping coefficients $\alpha = 293.215$ s⁻¹ and $\beta = 4.12624 \cdot 10^{-10}$ s). The material parameters of the PWAS (material: PIC151) can be found on the data sheet of the supplier PI Ceramic GmbH. The mesh of straight lug and tapered lug geometries exclusively consists of 8-node linear brick elements (in Abaqus nomenclature C3D8). The PWAS has a rectangular flat shape and dimensions of $10 \times 10 \times 0.2$ mm³. It is meshed with 8-node linear piezoelectric brick elements (in Abaqus nomenclature C3D8E) and is attached to the lug geometry using tie constraints (no adhesive layers between lug part and PWAS are modeled to reduce mesh effort and simulation time). The simulations include pristine (no crack) and cracked FE models. The cracks with lengths in a range of 0.5 mm–3 mm are modeled using the seam functionality of Abaqus, which produces idealized cracks without any gaps. The meshes of pristine and cracked models are identical except for some additional nodes at the modeled crack resulting from the included seam. At the assumed crack initiation location the nodes within a range of $\beta_{in} = 90^\circ \pm 10^\circ$ are denoted by N_{AAC} (highlighted in yellow in Fig. 2).

In the current numerical investigations the upper surface of the PWAS (nodeset N_{IMA} highlighted in blue in Fig. 2) is excited by a sinusoidal voltage signal with an amplitude of $5\sqrt{2}$ V.

2.3. Method to estimate the crack lengths in aircraft lugs

The methodology to identify cracks in aircraft lugs with necked, straight and tapered shape is depicted in Fig. 3 and includes two main parts: 1) the model-based crack identification and 2) the monitoring of the structure by periodic EMI-measurements. The following paragraphs explain both parts of the methodology in detail.

2.3.1. Model-based crack identification

The first part comprises an identification of crack sensitive resonance frequencies f_i^{FE} and associated sensitivity parameters λ_i^{FE} . Crack sensitive resonance frequencies are found by using a validated numerical FE model of the

Fig. 3. Method overview.

pristine structure and analyzing the mean major principal stress

$$\bar{\sigma}_1(\omega) = \frac{1}{N_{AAC}} \sum_{n=1}^{N_{AAC}} \sigma_{1,n}(\omega), \quad (1)$$

where $\sigma_{1,n}(\omega)$ is the major principal stress extracted from FEM results for specified angular frequencies $\omega = 2\pi f$ and each node $n \in N_{AAC}$ (yellow nodes within the region of $\beta_{in} = 90^\circ \pm 10^\circ$ and the full thickness of the lug, see Figure 2). Equation (1) is preferably evaluated in a wide frequency range and relatively rough frequency resolution to save computational time. In general, a fatigue crack initiates perpendicular to the major principal stress. Therefore, it is assumed that resonance frequencies with large $\bar{\sigma}_1$ peaks are highly sensitive to initiating fatigue cracks in this region (Winklberger et al., 2021b).

Subsequently, detailed FE analysis of the conductance $G^{FE}(\omega)$ of a PWAS applied to pristine and cracked structures are performed in narrow frequency bands of 5 kHz with a high frequency resolution of 31.25 Hz around found crack sensitive resonance frequencies. The conductance $G^{FE}(\omega)$ is calculated for each angular frequency $\omega = 2\pi f$ by

$$G^{FE}(\omega) = \text{Re} \left\{ \frac{I(\omega)}{U(\omega)} \right\} = \text{Re} \left\{ \frac{j\omega}{U(\omega)} \left[\sum_{n=1}^{N_{IMA}} (Q_n) - j\delta\epsilon_{33}^T \frac{U(\omega)}{t_p} A_p \right] \right\}, \quad (2)$$

where $j = \sqrt{-1}$ is the imaginary unit. The electric charge Q_n is extracted for each node in N_{IMA} (electrode nodes of the PWAS, blue nodes in Figure 2) from FE results (in Abaqus Q_n is provided as field output RCHG, i.e., reactive electrical nodal charge). The subtracted term in Equ. (2) models the electrical damping and includes the dielectric loss factor $\tan \delta = 20 \cdot 10^{-3}$, the relative permittivity $\epsilon_{33}^T = 2400 \cdot 8.85 \cdot 10^{-12}$ As/Vm, the excitation voltage $U(\omega) = 5\sqrt{2}$ V, the thickness $t_p = 0.2$ mm and conducted surface $A_p = 79.875$ mm² of the applied PWAS. Then, as many peak trajectories \mathcal{T}_k^{FE} as possible are to be found by tracking the resonance frequency peaks f_k^{FE} in multiple spectra of models with numerically increased crack lengths using the peak-tracking methodology presented by Gerber et al. (2015). This algorithm tracks peaks of subsequent measurements within a predefined search window δf . In Gerber et al. (2015) the suggested search window size should be approximately ten times the frequency sample size. For the current investigations relatively large changes of resonance frequencies have to be covered, which requires a larger

search window size of $\delta f = 20 \cdot 31.25 = 625$ Hz. Additionally, each new peak of any trajectory is validated by a back compatibility condition, which makes the peak-tracking more robust than the simple algorithm used in [Winklberger et al. \(2021b,a\)](#). Hence, this peak-tracking methodology enables an automatic and reliable search for a large number of trajectories.

The final step of the model-based crack identification is to find an analytical function $\Delta f_{k,c} = f(a_c)$ for each peak trajectory \mathcal{T}_k^{FE} , where $\Delta f_{k,c} = f_{k,c} - f_{k,\text{pristine}}$ is the frequency shift and a_c is the numerically introduced crack length, see Fig. 1. However, previous studies ([Winklberger et al., 2021b,a](#)) suggest that especially trajectories $\mathcal{T}_i^{FE} \in \mathcal{T}_k^{FE}$ with a trend close to

$$\Delta f_{i,c}^{FE} = \lambda_i^{FE} a_c^2, \quad (3)$$

are clear and accurate indicators for crack initiation and crack growth. In Equ. (3) the frequency shift $\Delta f_{i,c}^{FE} = f_{i,c}^{FE} - f_{i,\text{pristine}}^{FE}$ is directly related to the quadratic crack length a_c by the crack sensitivity λ_i^{FE} , which is identified by a least squares fit. In this study the correlation coefficient deviation (CCD) is calculated between data points and the interpolated quadratic function given in Equ. (3), and only trajectories which satisfy $\text{CCD} < 0.03$ are considered for further crack length estimation (for further information on the CCD metric see [Giurgiutiu \(2016\)](#)). The chosen threshold of $\text{CCD} < 0.03$ provides a good compromise between quality and quantity – it is low enough for accurate quadratic trends and high enough to yield a large amount of identified peak trajectories.

2.3.2. Monitoring growing cracks by EMI-measurements

The second part of the methodology to estimate the crack length in aircraft lugs includes EMI-measurements of the monitored structure. The measurement setup and procedure are identical to the described measurements in [Winklberger et al. \(2021a\)](#) for necked lugs. Initially a single baseline measurement of the pristine structure must be performed. Measured resonance frequencies $f_{i,\text{pristine}}^M$ of the baseline measurement, which are closest to the numerically calculated pristine resonance frequencies $f_{i,\text{pristine}}^{FE}$ are chosen to build the initial frequencies (representing the pristine state) of trajectories \mathcal{T}_i^M . Then, the structure is monitored by periodic EMI-measurements, taken at similar structural conditions, i.e., at the same external loading. Each measured frequency spectrum is immediately analyzed, which includes the finding of resonance frequency peaks $f_{i,c}^M$ and their assignment to existing peak trajectories \mathcal{T}_i^M . Equally to the measurement procedure presented in [Winklberger et al. \(2021a\)](#), for the current investigations an artificial crack was introduced in each lug using a scroll saw (blade thickness of 0.3 mm). Each crack was enlarged in six nominal increments of 0.5 mm until a total crack length of 3 mm was reached. After each enlargement of the crack, its exact length was measured using an optical stereomicroscope Olympus SZX10 and a new measurement with the impedance analyser (IMA) was taken.

Finally, by a simple rearrangement of Equ. (3), the crack estimation after each c th measurement is done by

$$a_{i,c}^M = \sqrt{\Delta f_{i,c}^M / \lambda_i^{FE}}, \quad (4)$$

using the model-based identified crack sensitivities λ_i^{FE} for each i th trajectory \mathcal{T}_i^M and associated measured frequency shifts $\Delta f_{i,c}^M$. In the present investigation the estimated mean crack length for each measurement c is calculated by averaging $a_{i,c}^M$ over all trajectories i .

3. Results and discussions

The results for straight and tapered lugs are presented in the order of the method overview in Fig. 3. For the discussion of measurement results of the necked lug see [Winklberger et al. \(2021a\)](#).

Fig. 4. Simulated stress spectra of pristine structures in the range of 50 kHz–250 kHz for a) straight lug, b) tapered lug (for the $\bar{\sigma}_1$ spectrum of the necked lug, see (Winklberger et al., 2021a)).

3.1. Model-based crack identification for straight and tapered lugs

Using the numerical models of straight and tapered lugs presented in Fig. 2, the model-based crack identification starts by analyzing the mean major principal stress $\bar{\sigma}_1$ spectra of pristine structures. The simulation is proceeded within a wide frequency range of 50 kHz–250 kHz and a low frequency resolution of 250 Hz. The resulting stress spectra in the areas of expected crack initiation are depicted in Fig. 4. All resonance frequency peaks detected by the peak finding algorithm *signal.find_peaks* (included in the *Python 3.8* package *scipy*) are marked with blue crosses in Fig. 4. As described above, the largest peaks in each $\bar{\sigma}_1$ spectrum are assumed to be most sensitive to a crack in the investigated region. In this study, the ten largest peaks in each spectrum are selected for further investigation, which are highlighted with red dots in Fig. 4. In 5 kHz bands around these resonance frequencies FE simulations (applying the same model as for the major principal stress spectra simulation) with a higher frequency resolution of 31.25 Hz are performed to investigate the conductance $G(\omega)$ spectra for pristine and cracked lugs (the length of the introduced seam is enlarged by 0.5 mm until a maximum crack length of 3.0 mm is reached). For each of these spectra the resonance peaks are identified and numerous trajectories \mathcal{T}_k^{FE} are tracked, each starting at the peak frequency $f_{k,\text{pristine}}^{FE}$ of the pristine model and ending at the peak frequency $f_{k,c}^{FE}$ of the model with the largest crack. Quadratic resonance frequency peak trajectories \mathcal{T}_i^{FE} are identified by finding the best fit to the function in Equ. (3) and evaluating the quality of fit with the CCD metric. Trajectories with $\text{CCD} < 0.03$ are chosen as crack indicators. Identified crack sensitive trajectories \mathcal{T}_i^{FE} for all lug types are plotted in Fig. 5. For each of the trajectories \mathcal{T}_i^{FE} the pristine resonance frequency $f_{i,\text{pristine}}^{FE}$ as well as the parameter λ_i^{FE} are provided in the legend of each graph. For the straight lug twelve and for the tapered lug eight quadratic trajectories are found. A comparison of Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 for straight and tapered lug reveals that quadratic trajectories are not necessarily found around all of the ten identified largest $\bar{\sigma}_1$ peaks (e.g., for the highlighted peak at approximately 70 kHz none was found). Moreover, in some frequency ranges more than one quadratic trajectory could be identified (e.g. for the highlighted peak at approximately 113 kHz for the straight lug and at approximately 155 kHz for the tapered lug). These circumstances are not problematic as long as a statistically relevant number of quadratic trajectories is identified in the process. Otherwise, the number of highest peaks (ten in this study) and thus the number of investigated 5 kHz bands must be increased.

Fig. 5. Identified trajectories including parameters λ_i^{FE} of their closest fits for a) straight lug and b) tapered lug.

3.2. Monitoring crack growth in straight and tapered lugs

The next step after the model-based identification of crack sensitive resonance frequencies in the conductance spectra is the baseline measurement of the structure (measurement no. 1). The experimental setup and the specimen position of the baseline measurement for the straight lug is depicted in Fig. 6a (setup and specimen position are comparable for the tapered lug baseline measurement).

Fig. 6. Straight lug pristine measurements a) No. 1 in flat, b) No. 2 in lateral, c) No. 3 in standing, and d) No. 4 in flat (180°) specimen position. Necked and tapered lug specimens shown are subsequently measured in similar positions, which is not depicted here.

For the current investigations with straight and tapered lugs three additional measurements of the pristine structures are performed (measurement no. 2 – 4). For each of these preceding measurements only the positions of the lugs were changed marginally, as depicted in Fig. 6b to Fig. 6d. This procedure should simulate a crack initiation period, where no crack is present and the measured spectrum is only altered by, e.g., environmental influences or measurement noise.

Subsequently, measurements of lugs with introduced artificial cracks are performed as described in Section 2.3.2 (measurement No. 5 – 10). The setups for these measurements are comparable to the baseline measurement depicted in Fig. 6a. Directly after each c th measurement (No. 2 – 10) the crack length $a_{i,c}^M$ is estimated for each trajectory i using the measured (negative) frequency shift $\Delta f_{i,c}^M$ and the corresponding model-based crack sensitivity λ_i^{FE} , cf. Equ. (4). However, a real value for the estimated crack length can only be calculated by Equ. (4) if frequency shift $\Delta f_{i,c}^M$ and crack sensitivity λ_i^{FE} yield the same sign. As all identified crack sensitivities λ_i^{FE} are negative (see Fig. 5) only frequency shifts $\Delta f_{i,c}^M < 0$ are admitted. A positive $\Delta f_{i,c}^M$ in Equ. (4) would yield an imaginary crack length.

Two measures are taken to address these issues. First, trajectories which yield a positive $\Delta f_{i,c}^M$ in any measurement c in which the median of measured $\Delta f_{i,c}^M$ of all trajectories i is negative are ignored for the crack length estimation. Second, any positive $\Delta f_{i,c}^M$ in remaining trajectories are set to zero, and hence, results in a zero estimated crack length (e.g., see measurement No. 4 in Fig. 7b).

Fig. 7 depicts the results of crack length estimation in a box plot for the straight and tapered lug for measurement No. 1 – 10. All measured data points are connected by straight lines for better visualization. The optically measured crack lengths are given as blue stars. The estimated crack lengths for each trajectory are plotted with various black symbols and dashed lines. The legend in Fig. 7 specifies the pristine resonance frequency of measured trajectories i (missing trajectories have been sorted out by the first measure described in the previous paragraph, cf. Fig. 5). The mean estimated crack lengths are given as red filled circles. The given boxes indicate the 5th and 95th percentiles of plotted estimated crack lengths and their median is given as horizontal orange line.

Fig. 7. Estimated lengths of cracks at $\beta_{in} = 90^\circ$ in a) straight lugs and b) tapered lugs.

Considering all identified and feasible trajectories the results of estimated crack lengths of cracks at $\beta_{in} = 90^\circ$ in straight and tapered lugs are satisfying and conservative. In both types of lugs the deviations between present and mean estimated crack lengths are within the submillimeter range. However, the crack length estimation between individual trajectories varies in some cases by more than 100%. For the straight lug the overestimation and scatter is more pronounced as for the tapered lug. However, the simulated crack initiation period (additional pristine measurement No. 2 – 4) is clearly distinguishable from measurements, where the lug had an artificial crack (measurement No. 5 – 10). Therefore, the presented methodology provides a clear indication of crack growth and a conservative estimation of crack lengths in aircraft lugs.

4. Conclusions

The present contribution extends an already published model-based method (Winklberger et al., 2021b,a) to estimate the length of cracks in aircraft lugs at an angle of 90° to the lug axis by two new lug shapes and additional experiments. Furthermore, the crack length estimation method has been improved by a robust peak-tracking algorithm and an automatic evaluation procedure.

Numerical FE models of straight and tapered lugs are used to identify sensitivity parameters for multiple resonance frequency peak trajectories. Such trajectories are found by subsequent analysis of the conductance spectra of a PWAS applied to pristine (no crack) and cracked (idealized cracks with no gap) models. For the considered lugs numerical results showed a high sensitivity of resonance frequency shifts to the change of crack length. Various relationships between resonance frequency shifts and crack lengths are found. In the present work sensitivity parameters of resonance frequency trajectories with quadratic trends are numerically identified and subsequently used to estimate the crack length in physical lugs by means of periodically measured conductance spectra of an PWAS applied to the shaft of

each lug. This model-based crack length estimation is possible, if validated numerical models are used. Present models of straight and tapered lugs are based on the validated FE model of the necked lug presented in Winklberger et al. (2021b). Therefore, for the lugs considered and the models used, the model-based crack length estimation method is able to approximate the true crack lengths in the submillimeter range. Furthermore, deviations between present and mean estimated crack lengths are conservative. Scatter in crack length estimations of individual trajectories is clearly visible. It is assumed that the deviation and scatter of crack length estimations are even larger if measurements are performed during a fatigue test. The additional damping due to clamping of the structure as well as variations in external loads may alter EMI measurements, and hence, recorded resonance frequency peaks significantly. However, the presented methodology enables a fast (during monitoring only one measurement, a subsequent resonance peak identification and peak-tracking is necessary), cost-efficient (only one low cost sensor must be applied to the structure) and reliable (clear separation of pristine and cracked lugs, conservative crack length estimation) structural health monitoring of aircraft lugs in controlled environments.

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